

×*Leucomoza*, a New Nothogenus in Cactaceae

MAARTEN H. J. VAN DER MEER

Abstract—The nothogenus ×*Leucomoza* (= *Denmoza* × *Leucosteles*) and the new combination ×*Leucomoza roseiflora* are proposed.

The name ×*Trichomoza roseiflora* was published in 2001 for a naturally occurring hybrid between *Denmoza rhodacantha* and *Trichocereus atacamensis*. Since the latter species is now placed in *Leucosteles*, a new nothogenus and a new combination are needed:

×*Leucomoza* M.van der Meer **nothogen. nov.**

= *Denmoza* Britton & Rose × *Leucosteles* Backeb.

<https://www.cactusnames.org/leucomoza>

×*Leucomoza roseiflora* (Font & Picca) M.van der Meer **comb. nov.**

≡ ×*Trichomoza roseiflora* Font & Picca — *Bradleya* 19: 59 (-66; figs. 1-12)
(2001)

≡ ×*Echinomoza roseiflora* (Font & Picca) G.D.Rowley

= *Denmoza rhodacantha* (Salm-Dyck) Britton & Rose × *Leucosteles atacamensis*
(Phil.) Schlumpb.

<https://www.cactusnames.org/leucomoza-roseiflora>

MAARTEN H. J. VAN DER MEER

ORCID 0000-0002-5182-9615

Roggekamp 379

NL-2592 VV Den Haag

m@vdm.nu